

UNITA Universitas Montium

Societal Impact Report

Phase I 2020>2023

Executive summary

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Introduction

The European Universities Initiative, launched by the European Commission, aims to transcend traditional educational models by fostering deep, strategic, and sustainable cooperation among higher education institutions across Europe. This initiative is designed to enhance the international competitiveness of European universities and to promote European values and identity by encouraging the formation of inter-university campuses that are integrated across multiple countries.

UNITA - Universitas Montium (hereinafter referred to as UNITA) emerged in its pilot phase from 2020 to 2023, initially comprising 6 universities: Universidade da Beira Interior (UBI), Universidad de Zaragoza (UniZar), Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour (UPPA), Université Savoie Mont Blanc (USMB), Università di Torino (UniTo), and Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara (UVT). Each institution brings three key characteristics to the alliance: they are strategically located in rural mountain regions including Serra da Estrela, Pyrenees, Alps, and Banat; they are situated in cross-border areas of Southern, Central, and Eastern Europe, facing similar regional challenges; and they are located in countries where neo-Latin languages are spoken, thereby fostering linguistic diversity and promoting Intercomprehension. The alliance is committed to innovative teaching and research practices, particularly focusing on Renewable energy, Cultural heritage, and Circular economy.

In 2023, UNITA launched its second phase, incorporating 6 additional member universities (of which 4 full partners and 2 associated partners), the UNITA GEIE legal entity as a full partner, and expanding its thematic areas to include other topics. The activities of UNITA are structured around eight Work Packages (WPs), each with a specific objective aimed at laying the foundation for making the UNITA alliance a true European University.

Based on the Theory of Change (ToC) and impact pathways, the UNITA alliance has developed a comprehensive model for identifying impact indicators that align with its objectives. Each Work Package is responsible for several major activities, which lead to specific outputs, outcomes, and impacts.

This executive summary includes a summarizing table that illustrates the impact value chains - linking the activities to their direct effects (output indicators), indirect benefits (outcome indicators), and long-term transformative impacts (impact indicators). This methodology ensures a structured and measurable approach to assessing the societal contributions of UNITA's activities during its pilot phase from November 2020 to October 2023. The collected data cover all activities and their impacts on the internal UNITA community and the territories of the member universities, with a clear demarcation when the scope is limited to specific areas or institutions.

In total, 8 impact value chains have been identified:

- UNITA as a participative, open, inclusive, and effective European university;
- UNITA for international and innovative student-centered education;
- UNITA towards enhanced multilingual Intercomprehension in Romance languages;
- UNITA R&I catalyzing change in rural and mountain regions through innovation in Cultural heritage, Renewable energies, and Circular economy;
- UNITA digital services;
- UNITA mobility for all;
- UNITA strengthening European Identity, Citizenship & Values;
- UNITA sustainability and dissemination to ensure the continuity and uptake of the Alliance.

This document is an executive summary in which only selected indicators are elaborated and explained in the text; the full version of the UNITA – Universitas Montium Societal Impact Report can be retrieved at: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10853036>, or by scanning the following QR code:

UNITA as a participative, open, inclusive, and effective European university

Activity	Output	Outcome	Impact
Building UNITA governance structure and processes	Creation of the UNITA governance and operational structure	Evolution of the UNITA structure in UNITA II with 6 additional new partners	UNITA institutional rooting: 97% of the internal academic faculties have participated in the Alliance's activities
Implementing UNITA management	6 UNITA offices in total have been established across all partner institutions	In total, more than 400 people have dedicated time to UNITA activities and 34 full-time administrative job positions have been dedicated to the Alliance	Added value of €631.903,00 from academics and staff contribution (considering only staff hours dedicated from the UniTo's staff to the Alliance)
Enhancing the participation of students, staff, and partners	83 individuals contributing to the internal governance and managerial participatory processes	66 Associated partners and 85 local organizations in local rural and mountain territories engaged in the activities of the Alliance	Enhancement of student democratic participation through the institutionalization of the UNITA Student Assembly and planning of a students' electoral process
Ensuring the Quality of UNITA	Establishment of the UNITA Quality and Evaluation Board (QEB)	Innovations in universities' self-assessment of teaching activities promoted by the QEB and an external evaluation agency	Dissemination of the innovative works of the UNITA Quality assurance system to the European higher education landscape through participation in 3 international events on the topic

UNITA's governance and administrative structure was designed to enhance participatory and democratic processes across its alliance universities. Implemented through a multi-level governance model, it includes the Governance Board, Advisory Council, Student Assembly, and Quality and Evaluation Board (QEB), ensuring active participation from all stakeholders. This structure has demonstrated flexibility and adaptability in UNITA II with the integration of six new member universities in 2023, showcasing its capability to quickly adjust and expand its collaborative framework.

A key feature of this governance model is the establishment of UNITA offices in each member university, central to the administration and local activities of the alliance. In total, 34 full-time positions have been dedicated to UNITA activities, supporting roles in communication, mobility, and financial management. Additionally, more than 400 university professionals, including academics and administrative staff, have contributed part of their time to the implementation of UNITA activities, further bolstering the alliance's operational success. Moreover, the UNITA operations have been integrated into the organizational setting of the member universities (97% of the internal academic faculties have participated in at least one of the Alliance's activities) This high level of engagement indicates the effective embedding of UNITA's processes within university structures, enhancing its transformational impact.

The Quality and Evaluation Board (QEB) of UNITA plays a crucial role in promoting governance transparency and enhancing teaching and assessment practices. It oversees the implementation of quality indicators and mission statements, regularly refining strategies to align with UNITA's quality standards. Among its successes, the QEB's impact extends beyond internal governance, demonstrated by its success in disseminating innovative quality assurance practices at international forums like the European Quality Assurance Forum. Additionally, as proof of the great relevance that UNITA places on QA, the Alliance has been the first in Europe to perform an external evaluation in 2023 conducted by the Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ARACIS). This evaluation, which included an in-depth review of UNITA's internal strategies and an onsite visit, highlighted significant strides made by the alliance in establishing a robust European inter-university campus.

Furthermore, the UNITA Student Assembly, created and led by students, has significantly advanced democratic engagement. It has drafted an internal statute and prepared for future democratic elections across all alliance universities to select Student Assembly representatives. This development is a key achievement in promoting an inclusive participatory governance framework and fostering a sense of belonging among the student communities of member universities to the UNITA alliance.

UNITA for international and innovative student-centered education

Activity	Output	Outcome	Impact
Supporting the personalization and recognition of study paths at the UNITA level	Establishment of the Hubs of Success (HoS) for counselling and supporting the UNITA students toward the internationalization of their curricula	6.061 students have consulted the hubs of success	36 UNITA days for student orientation
	Development of a digital cartography of courses offered by the member universities in the three strategic thematic areas: Circular economy, Renewable energies and Cultural heritage	Support in the development of 10 new forms of international education opportunities implemented at the UNITA level	Implementation of Matching Events on education leading to the co-design of 21 new international educational offers
Establishing the Teaching and Learning Centers network	Establishment of the teaching and Learning centers (TLC) network. The TLC network has met every month and comprises 30 participants	Organization of 9 workshop modules on innovative pedagogies for a total of 925 teachers from the UNITA universities	Ph.D. position and research on the topic
Assessing UNITA's quality of teaching and learning	Benchmark of UNITA universities' practices of Quality assurance (QA) of teaching and learning	Development and application of templates for surveys for students' evaluation of UNITA's educational offers	Identification of necessary skills and tasks from the TLC UNITA network to be applied in the internal UniTo Teaching and Learning Center

The UNITA alliance has made substantial strides in enhancing student-centered education through various innovative and international education initiatives. Central to these efforts are the Hubs of Success (HoS), integral components of UNITA offices at each member university. These hubs have directly supported 6,061 students in personalizing and internationalizing their study paths within the UNITA alliance, effectively contributing to their academic and professional development.

Standout achievements of the alliance in promoting pedagogical excellence have spurred from the newly established UNITA Teaching and Learning Centers (TLC) network. This network has organized nine modules on innovative pedagogies, attended by 925 faculty members from the alliance. These workshops not only facilitate the sharing of best practices among educators but also support the adoption of new teaching strategies tailored to the needs of diverse student bodies. Additionally, the alliance has organized 36 UNITA Days for student orientation across member institutions. These events, which were not initially planned, have been highly successful in engaging students and disseminating UNITA's educational offerings.

Further enhancing UNITA's capacity to develop new educational offerings, the alliance hosted several Education Matching Events aimed at promoting the ideation and implementation of new international educational offers among UNITA partners. These events, which were attended by 156 professors and vice-rectors, resulted in the co-design of 21 new international educational offers within the Alliance. These events are part of UNITA's strategy to continually develop and implement innovative international education opportunities, thereby expanding the educational scope for students within the alliance.

The UNITA alliance is profoundly shaping the educational experiences of its students, ensuring high-quality, innovative, and internationally-oriented education that aligns with both academic and regional development goals.

UNITA towards enhanced multilingual Intercomprehension in Romance languages

Activity	Output	Outcome	Impact
Analyzing the state-of-the-art in Intercomprehension (IC)	Report on the current state-of-the-art in IC practices and programs within and outside the UNITA community	Publication of free IC materials and training on the public UNITA website to increase access to IC resources	Organizational transformational impact: IC as a means of communication between UNITA staff
IC education activities to transform the UNITA partners' community	Development of an IC competence framework and 8 training models (for students, teachers, and administrative staff)	2.143 individuals comprising students, teachers, and administrative staff, have acquired IC skills through 44 courses tailored to the participants' needs	Creation of 6 different types of IC Micro-credential digital badges delivered to a total of 335 participants
IC research and dissemination activities to transform society beyond the UNITA partners' community	Establishment of a UNITA Ph.D. position for advanced research in IC in the UNITA context	Engaging in the IC academic discourse: active participation of UNITA representatives in 7 scientific conferences. UNITA also organized and hosted (in USMB) 1 international conference on the topic	Elevating IC research through the publication of 9 scientific articles and 1 Ph.D. thesis on IC
	Development and diffusion of guidelines for IC courses and dissemination activities	Expanding reach: introducing an IC Diploma for firefighters and facilitating learning activities for primary school students	

The UNITA alliance has significantly advanced Intercomprehension (IC) through the development and dissemination of specialized educational materials, courses, research, and dissemination activities. Free IC resources have been made widely accessible on the UNITA public website, resulting in 665 downloads by the end of 2023. Moreover, 2.143 individuals, including students, teachers, and administrative staff, have acquired IC skills through a total of 44 different tailored courses, including a 50-hour IC course for teachers - the first of its kind - and training for administrative staff for international UNITA communications. IC has also been fully integrated as a fundamental means of internal communication among staff within the alliance, enhancing daily interactions across organizational levels. As a long-term testament to these courses, 6 different types of IC micro-credential digital badges were delivered to a total of 335 people, contributing to their curriculum and professional development.

Additionally, UNITA has applied IC in practical settings, notably through the creation of an IC Diploma for firefighters. This program, developed by Université Savoie Mont Blanc and Università di Torino, equips emergency responders with essential language skills for effective communication in cross-border operations, thereby enhancing safety and operational efficiency.

Research on IC has also been a key focus, with the establishment of a dedicated Ph.D. position and scientific team that has led to significant academic contributions. This has resulted in the publication of 9 scientific articles and 1 Ph.D. thesis, furthering the theoretical understanding and practical applications of IC. These scholarly works were presented at various international scientific conferences, underscoring UNITA's leadership in promoting linguistic diversity and multilingual education.

Through these efforts, UNITA not only fosters multilingual practices and cooperation within its community but also extends its reach to influence broader societal and professional domains.

UNITA R&I catalyzing change in rural and mountain regions through innovation in Cultural heritage, Renewable energies, and Circular economy

Activity	Output	Outcome	Impact
Guiding UNITA universities' research toward transformative solutions for rural and mountain societal challenges	Creation of the UNITA's research and innovation cartography including 649 research projects to foster collaborative excellence in the three thematic areas	Establishment of an R&I Hub in the thematic areas of Cultural heritage, Renewable energy, and Circular economy for long-term strategies	UNITA's integration of 157 researchers in the R&I Hubs
Connecting research and learning	Development of UNITA's transformative Micro-credentials shaping expertise in Circular economy, Renewable energy, and Cultural heritage	Organization of 16 summer/winter schools with 199 total participants	Activation and sponsorship of 47 Ph.D. co-tutelles within UNITA of which 35 integrated into the R&I Hubs
Energizing the territories through research and educational activities in the three thematic areas	93 external stakeholders from the socioeconomic environment of the territories included in the R&I Hubs	Activation of 22 international innovation and research internships in companies, research centers, or institutions mainly focused on the three thematic areas	Activation of 49 self-funded UNITA joint research projects implemented by a total of 120 UNITA researchers

The UNITA alliance has effectively addressed challenges in rural and mountain regions by creating Research and Innovation (R&I) Hubs in the thematic areas of Cultural Heritage, Renewable Energy, and Circular Economy. A total of 649 research projects from member universities have been mapped across these areas. Moreover, these hubs have successfully integrated 157 researchers, and 93 external stakeholders from the territories of the Alliance have been integrated in the Hubs.

In terms of educational activities to foster innovation and a high level of educational excellence, UNITA has developed and organized 16 summer and winter schools that engaged 199 participants, enhancing interdisciplinary knowledge and skills across its key thematic areas. Additionally, the alliance has activated and sponsored 47 Ph.D. co-tutelles, with 35 of these integrated within the R&I Hubs, underscoring UNITA's commitment to advanced academic training and research.

UNITA has also focused on enhancing practical experience and fostering innovation through the establishment of international internships and research collaborations. 22 international innovation and research internships have been initiated, providing students with hands-on experience in companies and institutions focused on UNITA's thematic areas. Furthermore, 49 self-funded UNITA joint research projects involving 120 researchers have been implemented, largely driven by 2 successful UNITA Research Matching Events hosted by the University of Turin. These events have not only facilitated the creation of new research projects but have also strengthened UNITA's role in transforming the European academic landscape through collaborative and innovative research.

UNITA digital services

Activity	Output	Outcome	Impact
Implementing UNITA digital services	Set up of the UNITA Datacloud management tool	Establishment and maintenance of the UNITA public website	149.356 student cards issued at the UNITA level

The UNITA Alliance has effectively implemented digital services to support its educational and research activities across Southern Europe. A key development has been the establishment of the UNITA Datacloud, an open-source management tool that facilitates secure communication and document sharing among over 1,222 registered users involved in various projects. Additionally, the public website of UNITA, launched in 2021, serves as a dynamic online hub providing detailed insights into the alliance's activities, with dedicated sections for diverse stakeholders such as students, researchers, and the general public. This website acts as a central communication tool, continuously updated to reflect the latest initiatives and opportunities within UNITA. A significant digital advancement is the issuance of 149,356 European Student Cards (ESC), integrating physical and digital identification to streamline administrative processes and enhance the student experience across the alliance.

UNITA mobility for all

Activity	Output	Outcome	Impact
Developing new forms of original UNITA mobilities for all	Internal analysis to unfold the barriers and drivers to mobility through a survey participated by 13.662 respondents	Development of new forms of mobilities resulting in a total of 1.755 student mobilities activated within the Alliance	Growing interest by students in the new form of UNITA mobilities, resulting in an increased number of applications over the years
Development and implementation of UNITA Rural Mobility (URM)	Development and implementation of 313 URM	85 organizations from the local socioeconomic environment engaged in the URM	Activation of international research on URMs and dissemination activities to society
Digitalizing and facilitating mobility	Digitalization of administrative mobility processes and implementation of the UNITA flexibility window	Publication of a framework of skills that students gain through UNITA mobilities	A total of 2.473 UNITA mobilities were activated involving students, administrative staff, and academic staff

The UNITA Alliance has actively developed and introduced new forms of mobility for students, culminating in 1.755 mobilities across the Alliance. These mobilities include Virtual Mobilities (VM), Blended Intensive Programmes (BIP), Collaborative International Learning (UCIL), and Rural Mobilities (URM), each structured to accommodate different learning environments and objectives. Some of these are integrated into the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS), enhancing their value in academic progression.

The new forms of mobilities offered by UNITA have seen growing enthusiasm, as evidenced by the rising number of applications. For instance, applications for the BIP in Turin

jumped from 157 in the 2021-2022 academic year to 522 the following year, reflecting increasing student interest in these new mobility formats.

Among the new forms of mobilities, the UNITA Rural Mobility (URM) is particularly remarkable. As the name suggests, URMs are university internships for UNITA students in entities and companies in rural municipalities with the aim of creating new synergies in education, research and entrepreneurship and producing a net-positive impact on rural and mountainous areas across Europe, by opening mobility channels that reinforce the competences and improve the employability of university students. In total 313 URMs have been successfully implemented, engaging 85 local organizations from rural areas. This initiative not only provides professional training in rural settings but has also sparked international research interest, leading to projects focused on further understanding and disseminating the benefits of URMs.

Moreover, UNITA's commitment to mobility extends beyond students to include academic and administrative staff. In total, 2.473 mobilities were activated, of which 718 involved university staff categories, showcasing the broad scope of UNITA's efforts to foster diverse and inclusive mobility experiences within the academic community. These initiatives underscore the significant impact of UNITA's mobility programs on both personal and professional development across its network.

UNITA strengthening European Identity, Citizenship & Values

Activity	Output	Outcome	Impact
Promoting EU Citizenship and Values to the student community	Organization of 12 workshops on European Citizenship and Values with a total of 802 participants	Implementation of 2 virtual mobility courses on European Citizenship followed by a total of 800 students	127 Micro-credentials open digital badges for the European Citizenship course issued as long-lasting certification of impact
Promoting EU Citizenship and Values to society	Organization of 12 workshops in rural and mountain areas on European Citizenship and Values with a total of 396 participants	Organization of 9 courses on European Identity and Citizenship for rural communities with 248 total participants	UNITA university students acting as ambassadors for the promotion of EU Citizenship and Identity engaged over 1.000 local high school students
Promoting EU Citizenship and Values through research	Organization of an open conference on European Citizenship	UNITA promotes interest in EU Citizenship research to the student community through prizes for master's and bachelor's theses	Activation of a Ph.D. position on EU Citizenship

The UNITA Alliance has launched comprehensive initiatives to promote European Citizenship and Values, significantly impacting both student and societal levels across its member regions. At the student level, UNITA organized 12 workshops attended by 802 participants, exploring European identity and citizenship. These efforts were supplemented by two virtual mobility courses, which attracted a total of 800 students and covered key aspects of the European Construction Process through modules in History, Economy, Sustainable

Development, and Law. Recognizing achievement and engagement, 127 open digital badges were issued as long-lasting certifications of acquired competences and skills.

For the wider society, particularly in rural and mountain areas, UNITA organized an additional 12 workshops with 396 participants, followed by 9 specialized courses on European Identity and Citizenship, collectively engaging 248 individuals from these communities. These initiatives aimed to deepen the understanding of EU values, with the workshops and courses tailored to address the unique perspectives and needs of these regions.

A standout project includes UNITA university students acting as ambassadors, promoting EU Citizenship and Values to over 1.000 local high school students. Different initiatives were activated in all the territories of the member universities, where students acted as ambassadors to their younger colleagues at the high school level. For example, the University of Turin engaged two classes from a local high school for the development of a European Civil Calendar. This engagement not only fostered awareness among the youth but also empowered university students, deepening their commitment to European values.

Moreover, the Alliance contributed to the promotion of EU Citizenship and Values through research. In this field, UNITA has made significant strides by activating a Ph.D. position focused on EU Citizenship, which complements the educational efforts with scholarly research. Additionally, prizes for master's and bachelor's theses on European Citizenship were introduced, encouraging academic exploration and discourse on this pivotal topic.

UNITA sustainability and dissemination to ensure the continuity and uptake of the Alliance

Activity	Output	Outcome	Impact
Ensuring the uptake of the Alliance	Winning the EU call for European Universities	€10,2 million in additional funding equal to 204% of the initial budget provided by the European Universities call	Creation of the UNITA GEIE: the Alliance's legal entity <hr/> UNITA constellation projects
UNITA dissemination and communication	UNITA visual identity	UNITA is present on 5 social media platforms with a total of 4.952 followers <hr/> UNITA news: 20.000 subscribers to the UNITA newsletter	Activation of the UNITA podcast <hr/> 12 patronages issued by UNITA to various initiatives and events
UNITA's role model in shaping the EU higher education landscape	Publication of the Manual of Best Practices	Organization of the synchronized UNITA U*night across the member universities	193 presentations of UNITA in external events

The UNITA Alliance has significantly advanced its mission through strategic funding, robust dissemination efforts, and extensive participation in external events, thus reinforcing its role within the European higher education landscape.

UNITA's proactive engagement in securing additional funding has remarkably tripled its initial budget, with an additional €10.2 million achieved, representing 204% of the original funding provided by the European University Call. This financial influx has supported various UNITA initiatives and projects, demonstrating the alliance's capacity for growth and sustainability. A major milestone was the creation of the UNITA legal entity (GEIE), which was established to facilitate the operational efficiency and collaborative potential of the alliance. This legal entity, which has become an official partner of the Alliance in phase II, enables UNITA to function as a fully integrated European entity, enhancing its capability to manage and expand its projects effectively.

UNITA has developed a comprehensive communication strategy that includes a strong visual identity, active engagement on social media platforms, and a widely subscribed newsletter. With a presence on five major social media platforms, UNITA has gathered nearly 5,000 followers, facilitating regular interaction with its academic and broader community. The UNITA newsletter, with 20,000 subscribers, serves as a vital tool for disseminating information on the alliance's numerous activities, including mobility programs and research opportunities. Additionally, UNITA has granted patronage to 12 significant initiatives and events by the end of 2023, further extending its influence within the European higher education landscape.

Moreover, UNITA has been prominently featured in 193 presentations at various international and external events, significantly enhancing its visibility and impact on the global stage. These presentations have covered a range of topics pertinent to the alliance's objectives and have showcased UNITA's role as a leader in promoting innovative educational practices and collaborative projects. This active participation underscores UNITA's commitment to sharing its insights and best practices, contributing to the broader discourse on the future of European higher education.

Through these concerted efforts, UNITA not only strengthens its internal capabilities and outreach but also solidifies its position as a transformative and enduring force within the European academic and educational sectors.

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